

Combining freestanding ferroelectric perovskite oxides with two-dimensional semiconductors for high performance transistors

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ABSTRACT

We demonstrate the fabrication of field-effect transistors based on semiconducting single-layer MoS₂ and an integrated thin layer of BaTiO₃ (BTO) dielectric, isolated from its parent epitaxial template substrate. The thin BTO provides an ultra-high- κ gate dielectric effectively screening Coulomb scattering centres. These devices show mobility values substantially larger than those obtained with standard SiO₂ dielectrics and comparable with values obtained with hexagonal boron nitride, a dielectric employed for fabrication of high-performance two-dimensional (2D) based devices. Moreover, the ferroelectric character of BTO induces a robust hysteresis of the current vs. gate voltage characteristics, attributed to the polarization switching of the BTO layer. This hysteresis is strongly suppressed when the device is warmed up above the tetragonal-to-cubic transition temperature of BTO that leads to a ferroelectric-to-paraelectric transition. This hysteretic behaviour is attractive for applications in memory storage devices. Our results open the door to the integration of a large family of complex oxides exhibiting strongly correlated physics in 2D-based devices.

The development of methods and tools to deterministically transfer two-dimensional (2D) materials in 2010¹⁻³ opened the door to fabricate artificial matter by simply stacking 2D materials on top of each other, without being constrained by the rigid limitations of epitaxial growth: lattice parameter matching, complexity of the technique, and price of the required tools.⁴ Since then, this emerging field of research, so called van der Waals heterostructures,⁵⁻⁹ has continued to grow at a tremendous pace. Novel physical phenomena¹⁰ and device concepts¹¹⁻¹³ have been achieved by these straightforward methods of combining 2D materials.

Apart from vertically stacking 2D materials, a great deal of interest has been focused on using these deterministic transfer methods to combine/integrate 2D materials with other families or classes of materials in mixed-dimensional van der Waals heterostructures.¹⁴ Within this context, the isolation of 2D non-van der Waals materials opens up an interesting avenue.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ In particular, the recent fabrication of freestanding layers of complex transition metal oxides of just a few unit cells in thickness²⁰⁻²⁶ provides a new research arena as this family of materials presents a whole plethora of strongly correlated physics that is scarcely present in only a handful of van der Waals 2D materials. The integration of these freestanding complex oxides with 2D materials, however, was not reported until very recently by two research groups in parallel with preparation of our work. In these two recent works^{27,28} STO thin layers are isolated freestanding and used as high- κ dielectrics for field-effect transistors based on 2D materials.

Prior to the isolation of freestanding layers of complex oxides, 2D materials were already integrated with complex oxide dielectrics epitaxially grown onto 3D oxide substrates to improve and add new functionalities to 2D-based devices.²⁹ These previous works show a glimpse of the potential of combining van der Waals 2D materials with freestanding complex oxides. Particularly appealing in this field is the use of ferroelectric oxides,

presenting a spontaneous polarization that can be reversed by a suitable electric field in the opposite direction.³⁰ This polarization influences the electronic properties of the 2D material-oxide interface, and its switchable character provides an additional tuning parameter for device operation. Memristive properties have, in this way, been added to 2D-based field effect transistors and tunnel junctions.^{31–40} As already achieved with the dielectric STO,^{27,28} any step forward in facilitating the stackable aspect of these ferroelectric components would immediately expand their potential applications, using the van der Waals integration strategy to fabricate novel hybrid 2D heterostructures.

In this work, we isolate freestanding crystalline thin layers of BTO, one of the most widely researched ferroelectric materials, and integrate them for use as a ferroelectric gate dielectric in field effect transistors based on single-layer MoS₂ semiconducting channels. We found that BTO acts as a very effective high- κ dielectric, screening out Coulomb scattering centres and yielding larger mobility values than those obtained with standard SiO₂ dielectric.⁴¹ Moreover, the current *versus* gate voltage traces of the MoS₂ field-effect transistors based on BTO dielectric present a very robust hysteresis, characteristic of the ferroelectric nature of BTO. This hysteretic behaviour can be used to fabricate low energy consumption transistors or memory storage devices. We compare the performance of the fabricated BTO-based devices with that obtained in MoS₂ transistors fabricated with hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) flakes of similar thickness finding comparable mobility values, indicating that the ultrahigh dielectric constant of BTO effectively screens out the charge impurities.

The BTO layers, 15-50 nm thick, were epitaxially grown by high pressure (pure oxygen) sputtering on (001) SrTiO₃ (STO) substrates covered by (10 nm) La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}MnO₃ (LSMO) epitaxial buffer layers. The LSMO layer is used as a sacrificial layer to enable the BTO delamination. We take advantage of the fact that a HCl and KI based solution etches

LSMO very effectively without damaging the BTO film to release the BTO from the parent substrate (see Methods). Prior to the LSMO etching, a Gel-Film square (Gel-Film WF 4× 6.0 mil by Gel-Pac®) is adhered to the BTO surface to facilitate the handling of the BTO once it detaches from the parent substrate. Figure 1a illustrates the steps employed to delaminate the BTO layer from its parent substrate and Figure 1b shows an optical image of a Gel-Film with a ~2 by 2 mm² BTO layer (25 nm thick), obtained after the release process.

Figure 1. Isolation of freestanding BTO thin films. (a) Steps for the isolation of freestanding BTO films. A thin film of LSMO (10 nm) is epitaxially grown onto a STO substrate and subsequently a 15-50 nm BTO film is epitaxially grown on top. Then a Gel-Film substrate is adhered to the BTO surface and the stack is immersed in an etching solution (0.5 ml HCl (37%), 0.5 ml KI (3M), 10 ml H₂O) that attacks selectively the LSMO and releases the BTO film. (b) Picture of a Gel-Film carrier substrate with a macroscopic film of BTO (25 nm thick) on its surface.

The structure and composition of as-isolated BTO freestanding layers were characterized by high resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy and electron energy loss spectroscopy (STEM-EELS). Figure 2a shows a high angle annular dark field (HAADF) image of an as-isolated freestanding BTO layer released from the substrate and transferred onto a standard Si₃N₄ holey membrane. Details about sample preparation can be found in the Methods section. Atomic resolution HAADF characterization of the same flake along the (001) direction evidences a highly ordered perovskite structure, as shown in the image of Figure 2b. Occasionally, stacking faults or other growth defects were

observed in the images. EELS spectra at the Ti- $L_{2,3}$ and O- K edges were measured over the same region (see Figure 2c). Ti- $L_{2,3}$ edge fine structure shows a clear splitting between t_{2g} and e_g peaks, characteristic of a 4+ Ti oxidation state, as expected from the BTO bulk stoichiometry. Quantification of the Ti oxidation state was carried out using a multiple linear least squares fitting (MLLS) procedure to LaTiO_3 (Ti^{3+}) and BaTiO_3 bulk (Ti^{4+}) reference spectra and averaged values of 3.99 ± 0.01 were obtained.⁴² We additionally characterized the freestanding BTO flakes using optical microscopy, Raman spectroscopy, and photoluminescence spectroscopy (see Supporting Information Figs S1 and S2).

Functional characterization of the as-isolated BTO layers was performed by Piezoresponse Force microscopy (PFM) to assess the preservation of the ferroelectric character and its switchable nature with applied electric fields. For this purpose, the BTO layers were transferred to Au-coated SiO_2/Si substrates (bottom electrode) while the conductive AFM-probe is used as the mobile top electrode. Figure 2d shows a PFM phase map for a BTO sample of similar characteristics as those used for device fabrication subjected to domain writing by patterning a box-in-box design with opposite tip voltages (+5 and -5 V) above the coercive voltages. This result demonstrates that the ferroelectricity in the BTO films survives even in freestanding (peeled off from the parent epitaxy template substrate) form. Figure 2e shows a representative hysteresis loop on a selected location of the BTO flake. The reversal of the phase signal and the butterfly-like amplitude loop are the footprint of the 180° polarization switching. The phase loop is quite symmetric with respect to the sign of the applied voltage. From similar cycles acquired at different locations of the same flake (see Supporting Information Fig S3) we obtain coercive voltages of $3.1 \pm 0.6\text{V}$ and $-2.4 \pm 0.3\text{V}$ for the positive and negative regions, respectively. Asymmetric loops had also been measured in some of the flakes of

different thickness (Supporting Information Fig S3), presenting a shift to the negative applied tip voltages. This negative imprint corresponds to a preferred down-polarization state of the BTO, which was also found for similar heterostructures using non-freestanding BTO thin films.⁴³

Figure 2. Structural, chemical, and ferroelectric characterization of freestanding BTO thin films. (a) Z-contrast Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) low-magnification image of a 30 nm freestanding BTO flake transferred over a holey Si₃N₄ membrane. (b) Atomic resolution image showing the atomically sharp edge of the BTO flake viewed along the [001] direction. (c) Electron energy loss spectra of the TiL_{2,3} and OK edges acquired over the freestanding BTO flake. (d) PFM phase image on a 40 nm thick BTO flake after ferroelectric domain engineering by pooling a box-in-box pattern with tip voltages of +5V and -5V. (e) Local PFM amplitude (orange) and phase (black) hysteresis curves acquired on the transferred BTO flake.

In the following we show that the robust ferroelectric state of the single crystalline freestanding BTO layers can be used in combination with single-layer MoS₂ layers to engineer a field effect device. For the device fabrication, a piece of Nitto SPV 224 tape is adhered onto the Gel-Film substrate with the thin BTO layer and peeled off suddenly. This leads to the transfer of smaller area (30 by 30 μm², approx.) ‘flakes’ of BTO that

have more suitable dimension for our device geometry. We have explored two different approaches to deterministically transfer the BTO flakes that will be used as dielectric between two gold electrodes pre-patterned on a SiO₂ (285 nm)/Si substrate (Figures 3a and 3b): a deterministic transfer based on the use of nail polish polymer and one based on deterministic transfer directly from the Nitto-tape (see Methods).

The semiconductor channel is then fabricated by transferring a single-layer MoS₂ flake onto the BTO flake and bridging the two pre-patterned gold electrodes leading to a van der Waals mediated electrical contact (Figure 3c). Briefly, a bulk natural molybdenite mineral (Molly Hill Mine, Quebec, Canada)⁴⁴ was cleaved with Nitto SPV 224 tape. Then the tape containing the cleaved micro crystals was put in contact to a Gel-Film surface and peeled off gently to leave some atomically-thin flakes on the Gel-Film substrate. The surface of the Gel-Film is then inspected under an optical microscope (Motic BA 310 MET-T) in transmission mode to identify suitable single-layers of MoS₂ (see inset in Figure 3c). Their thickness is first assessed by their apparent transmittance⁴⁵ and then double-checked by micro-reflectance spectroscopy to verify single-layer flakes.^{46,47} Once a suitable single-layer MoS₂ flake is identified it is transferred with the all-dry viscoelastic deterministic placement method.^{48,49} Note that, when the single layer MoS₂ flake is connected to a multi-layered portion, a laser trimming process was carried out to ensure that all the electrical transport occurs through the single-layer MoS₂ (see Methods).⁵⁰

Figure 3. Fabrication of field-effect devices integrating single-layer MoS₂ channels and a BTO dielectric. The bottom panels show optical microscopy images at different steps of the fabrication. The top panels show a cartoon with the cross section of the corresponding optical microscopy images to further clarify the geometry of the devices. (a) Two pre-patterned gold electrodes onto a SiO₂/Si substrate. (b) A 50 nm BTO flake is picked up from a carrier SiO₂/Si substrate (inset in bottom panel) and transferred in between the gold pads. (c) A single-layer MoS₂ flake is transferred from a Gel-Film carrier substrate (see inset in bottom panel) onto the BTO flake and bridging the two pre-patterned gold electrodes.

The devices are electrically characterized under high-vacuum conditions ($\sim 10^{-6}$ mbar) in a homebuilt vacuum probe station system.⁵¹ An in-situ annealing at 200 °C for 2 h at high-vacuum ($\sim 10^{-4}$ to 10^{-5} mbar) was performed prior electrical transport measurements to improve the gold-MoS₂ contact and to remove atmospheric adsorbates. Figure 4a shows source-drain current, at a fixed $V_{\text{bias}} = 5\text{V}$, while the gate voltage is swept from -50V to $+50\text{V}$. The inset in Figure 4a shows a collection of I_{ds} vs. V_{bias} curves (IV s hereafter) acquired at different gate voltages. From the slope of the I_{sd} vs. V_{g} (IV_{g} hereafter) shown in Figure 3a one can extract the field-effect mobility of the transistor:⁵²

$$\mu = \left[\frac{\partial I_{\text{sd}}}{\partial V_{\text{g}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{L}{W \cdot C \cdot V_{\text{sd}}} \right],$$

where $\partial I_{\text{sd}}/\partial V_{\text{g}}$ is the slope of the IV_{g} trace, L and W are the length and width of the semiconductor channel, respectively, C is the capacitance per unit area between channel and backgate electrode and V_{sd} is the source-drain bias. In our geometry, the capacitance

can be calculated as two parallel plate capacitors in series, one with SiO₂ and another one with BTO as dielectrics:

$$C = \frac{1}{1/C_{\text{SiO}_2} + 1/C_{\text{BTO}}},$$

where $C_x = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_x / d_x$ with ϵ_0 the vacuum electrical permittivity and ϵ_x and d_x the relative permittivity and the thickness of medium 'x' (SiO₂ or BTO) respectively. Due to the very high ϵ_r expected for BTO (~4000),^{53–55} in this geometry the capacitance will be strongly dominated by the SiO₂ contribution. This result is advantageous to extract accurate field-effect mobility values despite not knowing the exact dielectric value of the BTO ultrathin layer.

Figure 4. Gate tunable characteristics of 1L-MoS₂ field-effect devices using BTO, SiO₂ and hBN dielectrics. (a) Source drain current as a function of the gate voltage for a device integrating a BTO (48 nm)/SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric (see cartoon on top). (inset) Current vs. drain-source bias voltage curves acquired at different gate voltages. (b) and (c) Similar datasets to (a) but collected for a device using a SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric layer and a hBN (~30 nm)/SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric layer (see cartoons on top).

We fabricated and tested 5 devices integrating BTO dielectric finding two-terminal field-effect mobility values ranging from 5 to 57 cm²/Vs (see the Supporting Information, Table S1 for a summary of the characteristics of all devices measured). Those values are substantially larger than those typically found on devices fabricated using the same protocol but with standard SiO₂ dielectric (see Figure 4b) which are in the 0.1 – 10 cm²/Vs

range. Moreover, in order to put those large mobility values into context, we directly compare the performance of the MoS₂ transistors integrating BTO dielectric with that of a device fabricated following the same steps but replacing the BTO flake by a hBN of similar thickness (Figure 4c). Note that hBN is used in 2D-based devices because it is considered as an almost ideal dielectric substrate due to its atomically flat surface and very low density of Coulomb scattering centers.^{1,56} Interestingly, the mobility of the BTO based devices is comparable to that of the hBN ones (1 to 80 cm²/Vs for 4 measured devices) which we attribute to the very effective screening of the charged impurities due to the very high dielectric constant of BTO.^{57,58}

Another important figure-of-merit of field-effect transistors is the current ON-OFF ratio, $I_{ON/OFF}$, which provides information about how effectively the transistor can be switched OFF. Most of the BTO based devices show $I_{ON/OFF}$ in the 10⁵ to 10⁷ range, comparable with the SiO₂ (~10⁶) or the hBN based transistors (~10⁵ to 10⁸). One BTO device showed a poor switching performance ($I_{ON/OFF}$ of 10) which could be due to a poor quality flake or inadvertent gate leakage.

Given the ferroelectric character of BTO, it is important to study the transconductance curves both in forward and backward sweeps to draw our attention to the hysteresis. Figure 5a to 5c compares the current vs. gate voltage curves acquired while sweeping the gate from -50 V to +50 V and back to -50 V for MoS₂ field-effect transistors with BTO, SiO₂ and hBN dielectrics. The hysteresis of the BTO-based devices ranges from 16 V to 44 V, substantially larger than that of devices with non-ferroelectric dielectrics where the hysteresis typically arises from the polarizability of adsorbed or trapped molecules on the surface or interfaces. While ferroelectric-induced modulation in transistors is expected to induce counterclockwise hysteresis loops,^{59,60} a clockwise hysteresis is observed in Figure 5a. This inversion is actually a relatively common result already reported in 2D

FETs with ferroelectric dielectrics, first with graphene channel^{34,38,61} but also in transition metal dichalcogenide based transistors (including MoS₂).^{37,60,62,63} Most studies agree that there is a subtle interplay between the ferroelectric polarization and interfacial phenomena, attributing the unexpected clockwise hysteresis to the interfacial charge screening of ferroelectric polarization. Although our devices have been annealed in high-vacuum (200°C for 2 hours.) prior to electrical characterization, the adsorbates trapped at the interface between the semiconducting 2D material and the dielectric, that could potentially screen the ferroelectric polarization, are very difficult to remove. Moreover, oxide ferroelectrics are typically oxygen deficient, and the oxygen vacancies concentration is higher close to the interface than in the bulk. These vacancies can act as electron traps when the MoS₂ is biased at a positive voltage, and this could be another source of the clockwise hysteresis of the transfer curves.^{61,62}

To get further insight on the role of the BTO ferroelectric character on the electrical behavior of the devices, we performed temperature dependent analysis of the current *vs.* gate voltage curves, to follow the evolution of the hysteresis. These measurements can help to identify the origin of the hysteresis as shown for SiO₂-gated devices.⁶⁴ In our BTO-based heterostructures, increasing temperature brings an additional interesting phenomena: the ferroelectric to paraelectric transition of the BTO (above 120°C for bulk crystals).^{65,66} If the large hysteresis measured in BTO-based devices is related with the polarization of BTO, a change is expected when measuring above the transition temperature. Figures 5d and 5e present the transfer curves and the hysteresis (calculated as the difference between voltages at I_{ON}/2 for the forward and backwards sweeps in the current *vs.* gate voltage curves, see arrows in Figure 4a to 4c) as a function of temperature. From 70°C there is a decreasing trend of the hysteresis that almost vanishes above 150°C, in good agreement with the expected ferroelectric to paraelectric transition. The larger

hysteresis values are recovered upon decreasing the temperature back to room temperature. This behaviour clearly differs from that observed in the model SiO₂-gated device, which shows a steep increase above 150°C, frequently related to thermally activated oxide traps (close to the interface) that can capture and release electrons from MoS₂.⁶⁴

Figure 5. Characterization of the ferroelectric nature of the BTO dielectric. (a) to (c) Comparison between the hysteresis measured in the current vs. gate voltage curves for BTO (48 nm)/SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric (a), SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric (b) and hBN (~30 nm)/SiO₂ (285 nm) dielectric (c). (d) Dependence of the current vs. gate voltage curves as a function of the temperature. (e) Hysteresis of the current vs. gate voltage curves as a function of the temperature for BTO and SiO₂ based devices.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we present the integration of thin BTO layers, delaminated from the substrates where they were epitaxially grown, as ferroelectric dielectrics in single-layer MoS₂ field effect devices. Their high dielectric constant helps to screen out Coulomb

scatterers leading to mobility values comparable to those obtained in devices integrating hBN dielectric, considered as an almost ideal substrate for high performance 2D-based devices in the nanomaterials community. In the devices integrating BTO layers we observe a robust hysteresis of the current vs. gate voltage traces, very distinct with respect to the hysteresis observed when other dielectrics are used, which we attribute to the ferroelectric polarization switching of the BTO layer. A proof that the poling of the BTO layer is playing an important role in the hysteretic behaviour is obtained from electrical characteristics at different temperatures, finding that the hysteresis nearly disappears at temperatures near the ferroelectric-to-paraelectric transition. Our results are the first step towards the fabrication of 2D-based devices with BTO based ferroelectric dielectrics and, in a more general perspective, towards the integration of a large family of transition metal oxides displaying strongly correlated physical phenomena in 2D-based devices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Epitaxial growth of BTO thin films: 15 nm LSMO and 15-50 nm BTO thick films were grown epitaxially onto (001) STO substrates by pure oxygen (3.2 mbar) sputtering technique at high temperature (900 °C). Both layers were growth sequentially without breaking vacuum. Interfaces were atomically sharp with LaO termination planes of the LSMO manganite facing TiO₂ planes of the BTO as shown by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), combined with electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS). This growth mode yielded out of plane ferroelectric polarization, preferentially pointing downwards.⁶⁷.

Release of BTO thin films from their parenting substrate: The strained LSMO/BTO heterostructure is adhered to a commercial polydimethylsiloxane film (Gel-Film WF 4x

6.0mil by Gel-Pack®) and immersed at room temperature in a diluted solution of 0.5 ml KI (3 mol/L) + 0.5 ml HCl (37%) and 10 ml deionized H₂O, which dissolves the LSMO in an average time of 3 days and allows the delamination of the BTO layer without damaging its properties. The freestanding BTO is then transferred to a SiO₂/Si substrate.

Nail-polish deterministic transfer of BTO: The Nitto tape is adhered to a SiO₂/Si substrate that will act as a carrier substrate and the surface is inspected with optical microscopy to find a suitable BTO flake. The flake is then picked-up with a nail-polish deterministic transfer method⁶⁸ and placed between two gold electrodes pre-patterned on a SiO₂ (285 nm)/Si substrate.

Deterministic transfer from Nitto tape of BTO: we select the BTO flake to be transferred by optical microscopy inspection of the Nitto tape surface. The Nitto tape is then mounted into a deterministic placement setup to align the selected BTO flake between two gold electrodes pre-patterned on a SiO₂ (285 nm)/Si substrate. By gently pressing the tape against the substrate and peeling off very slowly with the help of the micrometer manual actuator of the transfer setup one can transfer the BTO flake onto the desired location.

Scanning Transmission electron microscopy: STEM-EELS characterization was carried out using a JEOL JEM-ARM 200cF aberration corrected electron microscope operated at 200kV, equipped with a cold field emission gun and a Gatan Quantum spectrometer. BTO freestanding flakes were transferred onto a holey Si₃N₄ membrane for STEM-EELS observation using the deterministic transfer method described above.

Piezoresponse Force Microscopy measurements: PFM measurements were carried out using a commercial AFM system and software from Nanotec⁶⁹ operating in ambient conditions. SiO₂/Si substrates with an e-beam evaporated film of 5 nm Ti and 15 nm Au were used for the PFM measurements. PtIr-coated commercial tips from Nanosensors

(PPP-NCIPt) were used and V_{DC} and V_{AC} voltages were applied to the tip while the sample was grounded. The drive frequency, drive amplitude (V_{AC}), and trigger force were ~ 52 kHz, 1-3V, and 200-500 nN, respectively. Hysteresis loops were measured in the spectroscopy mode at the selected locations. A sequence of DC voltages was applied to the tip (V_{DC}), with the V_{AC} voltage superimposed to excite the electromechanical vibration of the sample. Both, phase and amplitude of the vibration are recorded as a function of V_{DC} voltage. Amplitude signal yields information on the magnitude of the electromechanical vibration whereas phase signal relates to the orientation of the out-of-plane component of the polarization (upwards or downwards). Ferroelectric domain engineering was performed by poling box-in-box patterns with V_{DC} tip voltages above the coercive voltages and the V_{AC} modulation off. Subsequent PFM imaging shows the phase contrast due to 180° switching of the polarization, and the amplitude signal, proportional to the magnitude of surface displacement induced by the converse piezoelectric, showing a minimum between both domains.

Electrode deposition: Pre-patterned gold electrodes were fabricated by evaporation of 5 nm Ti (used as adhesion layer) and 50 nm Au onto a $\text{SiO}_2(285 \text{ nm})/\text{Si}(p++)$ substrate through a shadow mask (Ossila, E321) in an electron-beam evaporator system.

Laser trimming of the MoS_2 flakes: Laser-cutting of MoS_2 flakes were carried out in ambient environment with a confocal Raman microscopy system (MonoVista CRS+ from Spectroscopy & Imaging GmbH) using a 532 nm excitation laser with an incident power of 28.6 mW and a $100\times$ objective with an integration time of 10 s.⁵⁰

Electrical characterizations: All the electrical characterization of devices were carried out in a homebuilt high-vacuum ($\sim 10^{-6}$ mbar, $T = 20^\circ\text{C} - 200^\circ\text{C}$) chamber. A source-meter unit (Keithley® 2450) was used for performing the electrical measurements

between source and drain electrodes. Two TENMA programmable benchtop power supplies (ref. 72-2715) are connected in parallel to perform gate voltage sweeps between -50V and +50V.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information: Thickness determination of thin BTO flakes using optical contrast. Raman and photoluminescence spectroscopy of MoS₂ on BTO. Local PFM amplitude and phase hysteresis curves acquired on additional transferred BTO flakes. Summary of device characteristics for all devices measured.

Funding Sources

European Research Council (ERC) through the project 2D-TOPSENSE (GA 755655)

European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Graphene Core2-Graphene-based disruptive technologies and Grant agreement No. 881603 Graphene Core3-Graphene-based disruptive technologies)

EU FLAG-ERA through the project To2Dox (JTC-2019-009)

Comunidad de Madrid through the project CAIRO-CM project (Y2020/NMT-6661)

Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation through the projects PID2020-118078RB-I00, RTI2018-099054-J-I00 and IJC2018- 038164-I, PRE2018-084818

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 755655 ERC-StG 2017 project 2D-TOPSENSE), the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Graphene Core2-Graphene-based disruptive technologies and Grant agreement No. 881603 Graphene Core3-Graphene-based disruptive technologies), the EU FLAG-ERA project To2Dox (JTC-2019-009), the Comunidad de Madrid through the CAIRO-CM project (Y2020/NMT-6661) and the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (grants PID2020-118078RB-I00, RTI2018-099054-J-I00, IJC2018-038164-I and PRE2018-084818). Electron microscopy observations were carried out at the Centro Nacional de Microscopia Electrónica, CNME-UCM.

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